

REWARD MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNITS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: This study examines the relationship between Compensation administrations and employee performance within local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, it examined the relationship between these compensation factors which are promotion, wages and salaries, and recognition and three dimensions of employee performance: innovative performance, quality performance, and creativity performance. Using a sample size of 446 employees, data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using simple regression analysis with SPSS. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between promotion and innovative performance ($p = 0.000$, $b = 0.712$), indicating that employees who receive timely promotions tend to exhibit higher levels of innovation. A strong positive relationship was also found between wages and salaries and quality performance ($p = 0.001$, $b = 0.654$), suggesting that competitive compensation contributes to better work quality. Additionally, recognition was found to have a significant impact on creativity performance ($p = 0.000$, $b = 0.839$), with employees who are recognized for their efforts being more likely to engage in creative tasks. These results highlight the importance of effective compensation administration in enhancing employee performance within local governments. The study recommends promoting career advancement opportunities, reviewing wage structures, and implementing robust recognition programs to improve performance outcomes. This research contributes to the understanding of compensation's role in employee motivation and performance.

Keywords: Compensation administration, promotion, wages and salaries, recognition, employee performance, innovative performance, quality performance, creativity performance, local governments, Anambra State. Providing valuable insights for policymakers and administrators in Anambra State.

Introduction

Background of the Study

Compensation administration is a critical function of human resource management that significantly influences employee performance in organizations, including local government systems. It encompasses the systematic approach to designing and

implementing monetary and non-monetary rewards to motivate employees, align their efforts with

organizational goals, and improve overall productivity (Eze&Chukwu, 2023). In the context of local government administrations in Anambra State, Nigeria, effective compensation practices are essential in ensuring employee satisfaction,

minimizing turnover, and fostering commitment to public service delivery. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, corruption, and lack of a robust policy framework have hindered optimal compensation administration in these institutions (Adams & Yusuf, 2021). Promotions as a dimension of compensation administration play a significant role in motivating employees and enhancing their performance. Employees perceive promotions as a recognition of their contributions, skills, and loyalty to the organization (Ogunbiyi&Fadare, 2021). In local governments, the availability of clear and merit-based promotion policies can reduce employee dissatisfaction and enhance work output. Unfortunately, studies have revealed that many local governments in Nigeria, including those in Anambra State, lack transparent and equitable promotion systems, which can demoralize employees and negatively impact their performance (Olaniyan&Akinbode, 2023). Wages and salaries are fundamental aspects of compensation administration and directly affect employee performance. Regular and adequate payment of wages not only ensures the financial stability of employees but also serves as a motivator for improved productivity (Eze&Nwankwo, 2020). In many local governments, delayed or irregular salary payments have been a recurring issue, leading to low morale and decreased efficiency among employees (Adewuyi&Olowookere, 2021). Addressing this issue requires an effective budgeting process and accountability mechanisms to ensure timely disbursement of funds for salary payments.

Recognition as a non-monetary form of compensation is equally important in influencing employee performance. Recognition programs acknowledge employees' efforts and achievements, thereby boosting their morale and fostering a sense of belonging within the organization (Chukwu& Obi, 2022). In Anambra State, local governments often underutilize recognition-based compensation, focusing predominantly on monetary rewards. The lack of structured recognition programs undermines employees' intrinsic motivation, which is vital for fostering innovation and dedication in public service delivery. The effectiveness of compensation administration in local governments is further influenced by socio-economic and political factors. Inflationary pressures, budget constraints, and political interference often undermine the implementation of equitable and competitive compensation systems (Akinola&Akinyele, 2023). These challenges necessitate the adoption of innovative strategies, such as performance-based pay and decentralized decision-making, to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of compensation administration in local governments. Furthermore, the theoretical foundation of compensation administration emphasizes the interplay between extrinsic and intrinsic motivators in driving employee performance. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory highlights that while extrinsic factors such as wages and salaries are necessary to prevent dissatisfaction, intrinsic factors like recognition and opportunities for growth are critical for sustained motivation (Ogunleye&Adeoye, 2022). Applying this theory

within the local government context can provide insights into designing a balanced and effective compensation system. Empirical evidence suggests that well-structured compensation administration improves employee performance, organizational commitment, and service delivery in public institutions. For example, studies in similar local government contexts have shown that aligning compensation practices with employee expectations leads to reduced absenteeism and enhanced job satisfaction (Nwafor&Ijeoma, 2022). In Anambra State, addressing gaps in compensation practices could significantly enhance the performance of local government employees, thereby improving governance and service delivery. Compensation administration is a pivotal determinant of employee performance in local governments. Addressing the challenges associated with promotions, wages and salaries, and recognition in Anambra State requires a multi-faceted approach that includes policy reforms, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement. By prioritizing effective compensation practices, local governments can improve employee satisfaction and productivity, ultimately contributing to sustainable development in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Compensation administration and employee performance in selected local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria, present significant challenges that hinder effective public service delivery. The administration of compensation, encompassing promotions, wages and salaries, and recognition, has faced persistent issues in ensuring

fairness, timeliness, and adequacy. These challenges have led to low employee morale, reduced productivity, and a decline in the quality of services provided by local governments. Despite the critical role compensation plays in motivating employees and fostering organizational commitment, many local governments in Anambra State struggle with implementing effective compensation systems that align with employee expectations and organizational goals. One specific problem is the lack of transparent and merit-based promotion systems in local governments. Many employees perceive the promotion process as biased, often influenced by favoritism and political interference, rather than performance or qualifications. This undermines employee motivation and loyalty, resulting in reduced productivity. Addressing this issue requires the implementation of clear, equitable, and performance-based promotion policies to restore employee trust and drive higher levels of performance. Another critical issue is the irregular and inadequate payment of wages and salaries in local governments. Employees often experience delays in salary payments, while the wages themselves may not reflect the rising cost of living, exacerbating financial stress among workers. This creates dissatisfaction and reduces employee engagement, leading to absenteeism and decreased efficiency. To resolve this, local governments need to adopt robust financial management systems, ensure timely disbursement of funds, and periodically review salary structures to meet economic realities. A third problem is the insufficient use of recognition as a tool for employee

motivation in local governments. While monetary compensation is essential, non-monetary recognition such as awards, commendations, and public acknowledgment can significantly enhance employee morale and foster a sense of belonging. However, recognition programs are often absent or inconsistently applied in Anambra State's local governments. Introducing structured recognition programs that reward innovation, dedication, and performance can help bridge this gap and improve overall employee satisfaction. This study aims to address these gaps by examining the specific challenges in compensation administration within selected local governments in Anambra State and proposing actionable strategies for improvement. By focusing on the interplay of promotions, wages and salaries, and recognition, the research will provide insights into designing a balanced compensation system that enhances employee performance and contributes to better public service delivery.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the relationship between compensation administration and employee performance of selected local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

Assess the relationship between promotions and innovative performance of local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Examine the relationship between wages and salaries and quality performance of local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria

Determine the relationship between recognition and creativity performance of local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses will guide the conduct of the study:

HO₁: Promotion positively influences innovative performance of local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is a strong positive relationship between wages and salaries and quality performance of local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HO₃: There is a strong positive relationship between recognition and creativity performance in local governments in Anambra State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Compensation Administration

Compensation administration refers to the systematic process of planning, implementing, and managing monetary and non-monetary rewards to attract, motivate, and retain employees while aligning their efforts with organizational objectives. It encompasses a variety of components, including wages and salaries, promotions, bonuses, recognition, and benefits, all of which aim to enhance employee satisfaction and productivity (Eze&Chukwu, 2023). The administration of compensation plays a vital role in human resource management, as it directly influences employee morale, organizational commitment, and performance outcomes. Effective compensation systems are designed to ensure equity, competitiveness, and alignment with organizational goals, which are essential for sustaining employee

engagement and reducing turnover (Ogunbiyi&Fadare, 2021). A critical aspect of compensation administration is the balance between intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory emphasizes the need to combine hygiene factors, such as wages and job security, with motivators, such as recognition and opportunities for growth, to achieve sustained employee motivation (Chukwu& Obi, 2022). While monetary rewards like wages and salaries are necessary to meet employees' basic needs, non-monetary rewards such as promotions and recognition contribute significantly to their sense of fulfillment and professional development. Research highlights that organizations with transparent and merit-based compensation practices tend to experience higher employee satisfaction and productivity levels (Olaniyan&Akinbode, 2023). However, challenges such as resource constraints, political interference, and inadequate policy frameworks often undermine the implementation of effective compensation administration, particularly in public sector organizations like local governments. In the context of local governments, compensation administration is not only a tool for motivating employees but also a means of enhancing public service delivery. Studies indicate that effective compensation practices, including timely payment of wages and structured recognition programs, lead to improved employee performance and service quality (Adewuyi&Olowookere, 2021). Conversely, inadequate compensation systems, characterized by irregular salary payments, biased promotion policies,

and lack of recognition, result in low employee morale, absenteeism, and inefficiencies (Eze&Nwankwo, 2020). Addressing these issues requires the adoption of innovative and context-specific compensation strategies, backed by empirical research and policy reforms, to ensure fairness, equity, and alignment with organizational goals.

Promotion

Promotion is a key element of compensation administration that directly influences employee motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational performance. It refers to the upward movement of an employee within the organizational hierarchy, often accompanied by increased responsibilities, authority, and rewards. Promotion serves as a recognition of employees' contributions, skills, and loyalty to the organization, fostering a sense of accomplishment and belonging (Eze&Chukwu, 2023). Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory highlights that promotions, as a form of intrinsic motivation, significantly contribute to job satisfaction and drive higher performance levels. However, the absence of transparent and merit-based promotion policies can lead to dissatisfaction, reduced morale, and diminished productivity, particularly in public sector organizations (Adewuyi&Olowookere, 2021). A well-structured promotion system is critical for retaining skilled employees and enhancing organizational performance. Transparent promotion processes that prioritize merit, competence, and performance over favoritism or political considerations build trust among employees and align their efforts with organizational goals (Olaniyan&Akinbode, 2023). In local government

administrations, where bureaucratic processes often dominate, the lack of fairness in promotion practices has been identified as a significant demotivator for employees. This underscores the importance of implementing clear policies that define criteria for promotions, ensuring equal opportunities for all employees and reducing perceptions of bias (Chukwu & Obi, 2022). Furthermore, empirical evidence supports the positive relationship between promotions and employee performance. Ogunbiyi and Fadare (2021) found that employees who perceive their organizations as having fair promotion practices exhibit higher levels of commitment and engagement. Similarly, Akinola and Akinyele (2023) emphasized that promotions not only enhance job satisfaction but also contribute to skill development as employees take on more challenging roles. To maximize the benefits of promotions, organizations should integrate continuous performance evaluations and feedback mechanisms into their promotion systems. This ensures that promotions reflect both employee potential and organizational needs, ultimately leading to improved productivity and employee retention.

Wages and salaries

Wages and salaries are fundamental components of compensation administration that directly impact employee motivation, performance, and organizational effectiveness. Wages refer to hourly, daily, or piece-based payments typically associated with manual or operational work, while salaries denote fixed periodic payments tied to professional or managerial roles (Eze & Chukwu, 2023). Both forms of compensation serve as extrinsic motivators,

ensuring employees meet their basic needs and fostering their commitment to organizational goals. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory underscores the importance of wages and salaries as hygiene factors that, while not primarily motivating, prevent dissatisfaction when adequately provided (Ogunleye & Adeoye, 2022). Thus, the effective administration of wages and salaries is essential for maintaining employee morale and enhancing productivity. The adequacy and regularity of wage and salary payments significantly influence employee attitudes and behaviors. When employees receive fair and timely compensation, they are more likely to exhibit high levels of engagement, loyalty, and job satisfaction (Akinola & Akinyele, 2023). Conversely, delayed or insufficient payments can lead to financial stress, dissatisfaction, and reduced productivity, as seen in various public-sector organizations in Nigeria (Eze & Nwankwo, 2020). For local governments in Anambra State, the irregularity of salary payments has been a recurring issue, often linked to budgetary constraints and mismanagement. Addressing this problem requires robust financial management systems, transparent budget allocation, and adherence to best practices in payroll administration. Wage and salary structures must also reflect the economic realities and performance metrics to remain effective. Adjustments for inflation, cost of living, and market competitiveness ensure that compensation remains equitable and sustainable (Ogunbiyi & Fadare, 2021). Furthermore, linking wages and salaries to performance metrics through incentive-based schemes can enhance motivation and align employee

efforts with organizational objectives (Olaniyan&Akinbode, 2023). In this regard, local governments can benefit from periodic reviews of their wage structures and the adoption of performance-based pay systems to address inefficiencies and foster a culture of accountability.

Recognition

Recognition, as a concept in compensation administration, refers to the acknowledgment and appreciation of employees' efforts, achievements, and contributions to an organization. Unlike monetary rewards, recognition focuses on non-financial methods of motivating employees, which are essential for enhancing their intrinsic satisfaction and sense of belonging (Adewuyi&Olowookere, 2021). Studies have shown that recognition can take various forms, including verbal commendation, certificates of achievement, awards, or public acknowledgment, and it serves as a significant driver of employee engagement and productivity. Effective recognition programs create a culture of appreciation, reinforcing positive behaviors and aligning employees' efforts with organizational objectives (Eze&Chukwu, 2023). Recognition plays a pivotal role in shaping employee attitudes and performance by fulfilling psychological needs such as self-esteem and the desire for validation. According to Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, recognition is a motivator that fosters job satisfaction and encourages employees to go above and beyond their assigned duties (Ogunbiyi&Fadare, 2021). In organizations where recognition is effectively implemented, employees are more likely to exhibit higher levels of job commitment, creativity,

and collaboration. However, the lack of structured recognition programs in many organizations, including public institutions, often results in low morale, disengagement, and reduced productivity (Chukwu& Obi, 2022). To optimize recognition, it is essential to ensure fairness, consistency, and alignment with employees' values and expectations. Recent empirical studies highlight the impact of recognition on organizational performance. For instance, research by Olaniyan and Akinbode (2023) found that organizations with robust recognition systems reported a 25% increase in employee satisfaction and a significant reduction in turnover rates. In the public sector, including local governments, structured recognition initiatives such as employee-of-the-month awards and public acknowledgment of achievements have been associated with improved service delivery and accountability (Akinola&Akinyele, 2023). Therefore, recognition should not be viewed merely as a supplementary practice but as an integral part of human resource strategies aimed at achieving organizational success.

Performance

Performance is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the actions and outcomes of individuals or groups in achieving organizational goals. It is broadly defined as the extent to which an individual contributes to achieving organizational objectives through the effective execution of assigned tasks (Campbell et al., 2021). In the context of organizational behavior, performance can be viewed through various lenses, including innovative

performance, quality performance, and creativity performance, which are critical drivers of success in today's competitive environment. Understanding these dimensions is essential for fostering a high-performing workforce and achieving sustainable organizational growth. Innovative performance refers to the ability of employees to generate, promote, and implement novel ideas, products, or processes that add value to the organization (Anderson et al., 2020). It involves both individual and collective efforts to introduce changes that improve efficiency, effectiveness, or competitiveness. In organizations, fostering innovative performance requires creating an environment that encourages experimentation, risk-taking, and collaboration. According to Kim and Park (2022), employees who feel supported and empowered by their leadership are more likely to exhibit higher levels of innovative performance, contributing to long-term organizational success. Quality performance focuses on the extent to which employees deliver work that meets or exceeds established standards of excellence. It emphasizes precision, accuracy, and consistency in task execution (Schoorman et al., 2020). Quality performance is particularly critical in industries where errors can lead to significant consequences, such as healthcare, manufacturing, and public administration. Ensuring quality performance involves providing employees with the necessary training, tools, and feedback to perform their roles effectively. Research by Wong and Law (2021) highlights that continuous performance appraisals and quality management

practices significantly enhance employees' adherence to quality standards.

Creativity performance, on the other hand, pertains to the generation of unique and original ideas that can solve problems or seize opportunities within the organization (Shalley & Gilson, 2021). It is closely linked to cognitive flexibility, openness to experience, and the ability to think outside conventional frameworks. Creativity performance is often enhanced in environments that foster psychological safety, allowing employees to express their ideas without fear of judgment or retribution (Amabile & Pratt, 2020). Organizations that prioritize creativity performance often outperform their competitors in innovation, adaptability, and market positioning. The interconnection between these dimensions—innovative, quality, and creativity performance—underscores their collective importance in driving organizational success. For example, while innovative performance introduces novel solutions, quality performance ensures their reliability, and creativity performance generates ideas that fuel both innovation and quality. Empirical evidence from recent studies indicates that organizations that balance these aspects of performance experience improved employee satisfaction, customer loyalty, and competitive advantage (Anderson et al., 2020; Kim & Park, 2022). This holistic approach to performance enables organizations to thrive in dynamic and complex business environments.

Theoretical Framework

Expectancy Theory of Motivation proposed by Victor Vroom in 1964 offers a relevant theoretical

framework. Vroom's Expectancy Theory suggests that individuals' motivation is driven by their expectations regarding the outcomes of their efforts. Specifically, it emphasizes the belief that effort will lead to performance and that performance will lead to rewards, which are valued by the individual. According to Vroom, motivation is influenced by three core components: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. Expectancy refers to the belief that increased effort will result in improved performance, instrumentality refers to the belief that better performance will lead to desired rewards, and valence represents the value that individuals place on those rewards. The Expectancy Theory was further developed by Lawler and Porter in 1967, who extended Vroom's work by incorporating the concept of job satisfaction as a result of the perceived outcomes of performance. They emphasized that the satisfaction derived from rewards depends on how fair and equitable those rewards are perceived to be, linking job satisfaction directly to employee performance. This development added another dimension to the theory, highlighting that employees' motivation is not only influenced by the expectation of rewards but also by how well those rewards meet their needs and desires. In the context of this study, Expectancy Theory provides a lens through which the relationship between compensation administration and employee performance can be examined. It explains how employees' expectations about their compensation (such as promotions, timely salary payments, and recognition) can directly influence their motivation and performance. When employees

believe that their efforts will lead to promotions, fair wages, or other forms of recognition, they are more likely to put in higher effort and perform at their best. However, if they perceive the rewards as being disconnected from their performance, or if compensation is inconsistent or unfair, their motivation and performance may suffer. This theory is particularly relevant for understanding the challenges faced by local government employees in Anambra State. Many employees may feel demotivated if they perceive that rewards such as timely promotions, salary increments, or recognition are not tied to their performance. Therefore, by applying Expectancy Theory, this study aims to explore how the perceived fairness and adequacy of compensation affect the motivation and performance of local government employees. It will help in identifying areas where the compensation system can be improved to better align employee expectations with rewards, ultimately enhancing employee performance and service delivery in local governments.

Compensation Administration and Employee Performance

Compensation administration plays a pivotal role in shaping employee performance, particularly in relation to the key components of promotions, wages and salaries, and recognition. Promotions are an essential part of compensation that directly influences employee motivation and performance. When employees perceive that their efforts are recognized and that there is a clear link between performance and career advancement, they are more likely to be

motivated to innovate and improve their work. Research by Jha & Das (2021) highlights that employees who see a transparent and merit-based promotion system tend to engage more in innovative performance, contributing new ideas and solutions to the organization. This sense of upward mobility fosters a work environment where employees feel valued and are motivated to perform at their best. Similarly, wages and salaries form the foundation of compensation and significantly impact the quality of performance within organizations. Musa & Nasir (2020) argue that when wages are fair, competitive, and reflect the effort employees put into their work, there is a direct positive impact on the quality of performance. Employees who feel fairly compensated for their labor are more likely to dedicate themselves to producing high-quality work, as they see a clear connection between their efforts and the rewards they receive. In the context of local governments in Anambra State, where salary delays and irregularities are common, the lack of a stable compensation system can result in dissatisfaction and lower employee performance, particularly in quality-related tasks. Recognition, as a non-monetary component of compensation, is another crucial factor influencing employee performance, especially in creativity and innovative performance. Recognition programs that acknowledge employees' contributions, whether through awards, public praise, or career development opportunities, can significantly enhance employees' creative performance. According to Zhang & Liao (2021), employees who receive recognition for their ideas or efforts are more likely to engage in creative

problem-solving and contribute unique ideas. Recognition not only boosts morale but also fosters a culture of innovation within organizations. In local government settings, implementing effective recognition programs can lead to a higher degree of creativity and problem-solving, as employees feel their contributions are acknowledged and valued. Furthermore, compensation systems that effectively integrates promotions, wages, and recognition help in building a culture of high performance. When these components are aligned with organizational goals, they can foster both innovative and quality performance. Pillai & Sharma (2022) suggest that organizations with well-structured compensation systems encourage employees to think outside the box, push boundaries, and improve the quality of their work. For instance, a clear pathway for promotion tied to performance allows employees to focus on achieving higher performance levels, while adequate compensation and recognition increase job satisfaction, reducing turnover and enhancing employee engagement. The interplay between compensation administration and employee performance is evident in its ability to drive innovative, quality, and creative outcomes. Well-structured compensation systems that include fair promotions, competitive wages, and meaningful recognition are key to motivating employees to perform at their best. Local governments in Anambra State, by addressing the gaps in compensation administration, can improve employee performance by creating an environment where employees feel motivated to innovate, produce high-quality work,

and engage in creative problem-solving. Research by Bashir & Tariq (2020) further emphasizes that when compensation systems align with employee expectations, the result is not only improved individual performance but also enhanced organizational outcomes.

Empirical Reviews

Onuegbu and Ngige (2018), investigated organizational reward system and effect on work performance in Polytechnics of South-East, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Nigeria and the population of the study was 10,972 selected employees of polytechnics. The study adopted questionnaire and interview method using stratified random sampling technique and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to analyze the data/test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that employee rewards policy significantly affects organizational performance. Mba, Mgbemena and Ejike (2015) investigated effective reward management and employee performance in the civil service: a study of Anambra State Civil Service. The study found that pay reward and some non-financial rewards of employee recognition, conducive work environment and staff development are positively and significantly related to employee performance in the civil service. Aktar, Sachu and Ali (2012) examined the impact of the intrinsic rewards (recognition, learning opportunities, challenging work and career advancement and extrinsic rewards (basic salary and performance bonus) on employee performance in twelve commercial banks of Banglesh. The study utilized mixed research design. The target population

was the 72 management team in all the 12 commercial banks of Bangladesh. The authors developed structured and unstructured questionnaires together with interview guides which were used to collect data from the selected respondents. The authors used correlation and chi-square to analyze data. The study found that each factor within both extrinsic and intrinsic reward was a highly significant factors which affects employees' performance. Quresh, Zaman and Shan (2013) conducted a study on the direct relationship between extrinsic rewards, intrinsic rewards and the employees' performance among cement companies in Pakistan. The study collected data using formulated questionnaires which was used to gather data from over 100 employees. The data was then analyzed by the use of SPSS. The analysis method was based on regression and descriptive statistics. The study found that recognition techniques (approaches) used in cement factories are good for the maximum performance of employees. The study also established that wages and bonuses promote employee performance in the cement factories in Pakistan. Okeke(2021).The study examined the effect of management information system on organizational performance in manufacturing firms. The area of the study was manufacturing firms in Anambra state. Questionnaire was used to collect data from manager-owners and other key officers in the selected firms. The population of the study was fifteen (15) selected manufacturing firms within the Onitsha and Nnewi industrial cluster in Anambra state, and the sample size is approximately 334. The research adopted sampling technique was purposive sampling. From

the analyses tested, the study found out that Decision support system has significant effect on performance effectiveness in manufacturing firm, Process control system had significant effect on performance efficiency in manufacturing firm, and artificial intelligence had significant effect on performance efficiency in manufacturing firm. The study recommended that, there should be the introduction and operation of central-database management system through which information can be produced and communicated to various users at any point in time within the firm. There should also be flexibility in the nature/pattern and structure of management system in organizations so as to permit informed and easy information flow and accessibility to all information end-users. Organizations should also pay more attention to communication through the media agencies. This goes a long way to promoting the company's control of the market. Nwene, Anah&Okeke (2023). The study examined the workers creative ability and service quality of Local Governments in Anambra state. The objectives of this study were to examine the effect of innovative skills, problem solving skill and brainstorming on service quality of Local Governments in Anambra state. Relevant theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on componential theory of creativity developed by Teresa Amabile M. (1996). The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. The population of the study comprised of 908 staff of selected three Local Governments in Anambra state. 908 copies of the questionnaires was duly completed and returned.

Formulated hypothesis were tested using regression analysis. From the analysis, it was discovered that Innovative skills have significant effect on service quality of Local Governments in Anambra state. Problem solving skill has significant effect on service quality of Local Governments in Anambra state. Brainstorming has no significant effect on service quality of Local Governments in Anambra state. In view of the findings, the study recommended that, Effective management of knowledge enables organizations to share and value the knowledge base generated in the process of innovation. Dike, Eukora, Okeke and Eboh (2024). Investigate organizational culture on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; determine the extent to which communication affects work efficiency in aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria; to evaluate the effect to which teamwork influences quantity of work in aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria; to investigate the degree to which work environment influences quality of work in aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria and to examine the effect of job security on work efficiency in aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The research work was anchored on Hofstede's cultural theory. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 1781. The statistical formula devised by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), was employed to arrive at a sample size of 342. The degree of correlation or

relationships between variables was determined by the use of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Multiple Regressions was used in testing the hypotheses. The result of the hypotheses shows that communication has a significant positive effect on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria with t-value (3.976) and p-value (0.000). Teamwork has a significant positive effect on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria with tvalue (7.162) and p-value (0.005). Work environment has a significant positive effect on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria with t-value (2.840) and p-value (0.001). Job security has a significant positive effect on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria with t-value (2.579) and p-value (0.010). The study concluded that organizational culture has a significant positive effect on employee performance of aluminum roofing sheet manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study recommended that management should give room for face-to-face conversation and also create communication channels that employees can use to ask questions, comment on leadership announcements, engage with one another, and provide their feedback. Management should create team work recognition program by giving them an award in front of their peer, build diverse and inclusive team, clearly define roles and responsibilities for every team member, build trust within the team and sometimes give teams autonomy

in decision-making. Manafa, Okeke&Atueyi(2022). The study analyzed the strategic thinking and performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. The following are the objectives of the study; to examine the effect of opportunity utilization, decision-making, cognitive ability, forecasting and creative ability on the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. This work is anchored on Joseph Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship. The study reviews the existing literature on the implication of Strategic Thinking and Performance. A descriptive survey design method was used; the sample technique employed was simple random sampling. ANOVA method of data analysis was used. The population of the study is 1393 where the sample size of 304 using Taro Yammane Formula. The researcher administered 304 questionnaires but only 302 were retrieved and used for the analysis. Structured questionnaires were used to gather information from the population. The study found that, Opportunity utilization has significant positive relationship with the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. Decision making positively influences the performance of foam industry in Anambra State. Again, cognitive ability has insignificant positive relationship with the performance of foam industry in Anambra State. Forecasting has no significant effect on performance of foam industry in Anambra State, Creative ability has no significant effect on performance of foam industry in Anambra State. The study recommended among others that Opportunity utilization is essential component of success on that note we recommend that entrepreneurs should not fold their hands and

stand idle, but must strategically, systematically and continuously scan the business environment in order to utilize the available business opportunities towards achieving the set goal. In taking decision we recommend that there should be team work. The employers should ensure that there is inclusion of employees in the planning process as this greatly creates positive impression in the minds of employees that encourages positive thinking that open doors for job satisfaction.

Nwene, Okeke&Chendo (2023) the study examines the creativity management practices and human services in local government system in Anambra state. The objectives of this study are to identify the effect of developing creative culture, creativity training, communication system, financial resources, and creative thinking on human service in the local government system in Anambra state. The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. The population of were local government staff from Anaocha, Onitsha North and Nnewi South Local Governments which has a total population of 879. Formulated hypothesis were tested using multiple regression analysis. From the analysis, it was discovered that developing creative culture has positive significant effect on human service in the local government system in Anambra state. Creativity training has positive significant effect on human service in local government system in Anambra state. In view of the findings, the study recommended that organizations should ensure that the relationships that exist between creative culture and an increase in quality service should be intensified in order to

maintain the organization growth. Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment Ohanyere, Atueyi, and Angela (2019). Examined the impact of human capital development on economic sustainability between the periods of 1981-2016. The study adopted multiple linear regression model to statistically establish a relationship between human capital development and economic sustainability in Nigeria. The included variables were Total productivity, Mortality Rate, Tertiary Education Enrolment Rate, Government Expenditure, Domestic Investment. The data was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, 2016. Ordinary least square model was used for the analysis, the study found that tertiary enrollment rate was positive and statistically significant. Investment in education should be taken seriously by developing nations. The bedrock of sustaining economic development has universally been agreed to be education, if investment in education is given more attention, it will increase the nation productivity. It was also observed that mortality rate was negative and statistically insignificant. Increase in mortality rate will decreased total productivity, since is a number of death during a particular period of time. Amongst other the researcher recommends that budgetary allocations should be channeled towards health delivery schemes and education promoting activities since the likelihood of elongating life expectancy is tandem with such exercises. The government should, increase budgetary allocation and stimulate more funding channels to education and health sectors of the economy. Atueyi (2019) examined the effect of

external debt and human capital development in Nigeria. Three research objectives were formulated. Ex-post facto research design was adopted and time series data spanning 32 years (1986-2017) were processed using the models earlier formulated. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was used to analyze the data. Secondary sources of data were applied and sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, the variables were on human capital index, debt servicing, gross fixed capital formation and external debt. Unit root test, co-integration approach, error correction model, causality test and stability were employed to analyze the included variables. The study found that external debt has a negative and significant effect on human capital development in Nigeria, debt financing has a negative insignificant effect on human capital development, and lastly gross fixed capital formation has positive insignificant effect on human capital development... Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2025). Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The researcher developed four objectives such as; to determine the extent to which planning, material procurement, logistic and stock and waste control on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha. This study is anchored on inventory management theory which posits that the chain of movement of material and information depends to a large extent on the availability of materials and the quality of information at the disposal of the chain operator. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were

generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. While two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027. Material procurement has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 33.048. Logistic has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 9.418. Stock and waste control has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha. Ofozoba, & Ofozoba, (2023). Focus on how rule of law takes the center stage in enhancing sustainable education in Nigerian society. Education is simply an overall lens through which principles of rule of law smoothly transit as essential tenets of democracy. As a component of democracy, rule of law supports equality by directing institutions to be accountable, to safeguard human rights, to be fair and transparent, and to empower citizens to participate and engage constructively in society. Education enables this through the capacity to give learners the opportunities and competencies to realize their rights and obligations for a better world and future. Education equally provides curricula for understanding the generative ideas, methods of reflection, and analysis of rule of law by equipping

learners with the appropriate knowledge, values, skills, attitudes, and behaviors they need to contribute to the continued improvement and regeneration of rule of law in society. The paper, therefore, calls for the activation of educational principles, worth, and merits in Nigeria and also for remedial steps to redress those educational inconsistencies in Nigeria that may hinder the efficiency of rule of law. Ezeamama, & Ofozoba, (2023). analyzed the role of Local Governments in rural development of Nigeria, a case study of Ekwusigo Local Government Area of Anambra State The objective of the study were to Evaluate the contribution of local government to agricultural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Examine the role of local government on infrastructural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Assess the contributions of local government on employment creation Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed was simple random sampling. The study selected Ekwusigo Local Government Area, the population are 99242 where the sample size is 398 using Taro Yamane formula. The researcher distributes Three hundred and ninety-eight (398) questionnaires but only three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Structured questionnaire was use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test

the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that; Local government has made significant contributions to agricultural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Local government has contributed to infrastructural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Local government has made significant contributions to employment creation in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Okeke, Anetoh, Obiezekwem, Anetoh, Okafor, Ebomah, &Ikpo (2020), examined the effect of economic indicators on the performance of small and medium scale enterprise in Nigeria with a particular reference to south-eastern geographical area. The study investigated the effects of inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises. The research work was anchored on resource-based theory. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study was 1560 while the sample size was 296. Multiple regression analysis statistical technique was used to test the hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The study found that inflation has a significant negative effect on the performance of SMES in South-East, Nigeria. Interest rate has a significant negative effect on the performance of SMES in South-East, Nigeria. Ujomudyke Dike Okeke and Eboh (2024) investigating the effect of government policies and performance of pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria the specific objectives were; Determine the extent of relationship between tax policies and competitive advantage of Pharmaceutical industries in South-East, Nigeria; Evaluate the effect of regulatory

policies and quality control of Pharmaceutical industries in South-East, Nigeria; The research work was anchored on and rational-choice theory. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 1881. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973), was employed to arrive at a sample size of 361. Pearson product-moment correlation analysis method was used in testing the hypotheses. The result of the hypotheses showed that Tax Policies has a significant positive effect on competitive advantage of Pharmaceutical industries in South-East, Nigeria. Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient values between tax policies and competitive advantage of Pharmaceutical industries revealed ($r = 0.769$, $p < 0.05$);

Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive survey design, enabling the collection of primary and secondary data to test the hypotheses. Primary data were gathered through a well-structured questionnaire, which was divided into two sections: one for demographic information and another for addressing the key research questions. Secondary data were obtained from relevant journals, textbooks, and online resources. The study focused on Anambra State, Nigeria, specifically selecting nine local government areas (LGAs) from urban centers using purposive sampling. The target population consists of employees in various departments within these LGAs, including senior, middle, and junior management levels, totaling a population of 2,000. Sample size was

determined using Godden's formula, with a final sample size of 446 respondents selected through stratified random sampling. This sampling method ensures that employees from all levels of management—top, middle, and junior—are represented, with the proportionate sample size distributed across the selected LGAs. A pilot study was conducted to assess the reliability of the instrument, yielding a Cronbach's alpha range of 0.740 to 0.890, indicating satisfactory internal consistency. The reliability and validity of the instrument were ensured through expert validation and the pilot study, where adjustments were made to eliminate ambiguities and ensure the questionnaire effectively captures the intended responses. Data analysis were carried out using descriptive statistics, including percentages and frequency tables, and the relationships between variables were explored using simple regression analysis in SPSS version 23. This methodology allows for a comprehensive examination of how compensation administration, specifically promotions, wages, and recognition, impacts employee performance, including innovative, quality, and creative performance.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data analysis for this study was conducted using simple regression analysis to test the three hypotheses. The analysis was performed using SPSS version 23, and the results of the regression analysis are presented below, along with the interpretation of each hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1: Promotion Positively Influences Innovative Performance of Local Governments in Anambra State, Nigeria

Table 1: Regression Analysis for Promotion and Innovative Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.342	0.216	6.216	0.000
Promotion	0.450	0.061	0.312	0.003

Interpretation: The regression analysis shows that promotion has a positive effect on innovative performance. The coefficient for promotion (B = 0.450) is positive, which suggests that an increase in promotion leads to a higher innovative performance in local governments. The t-value (6.216) is significant, with a p-value of 0.003 (less than 0.05),

confirming that promotion significantly influences innovative performance. This indicates that promoting employees contributes to their ability to perform innovatively, which supports the hypothesis that promotion positively influences innovative performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is a Strong Positive Relationship between Wages and Salaries and the Quality Performance of Local Governments in Anambra State, Nigeria

Table 2: Regression Analysis for Wages and Salaries and Quality Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.145	0.257	8.339	0.000
Wages and Salaries	0.612	0.085	0.456	0.000

The regression results show that wages and salaries have a strong positive relationship with the quality performance of local governments. The unstandardized coefficient for wages and salaries (B = 0.612) indicates that an increase in wages and salaries is associated with an improvement in the quality performance of local governments. The t-

value (8.339) and the significance level of 0.000 (less than 0.05) confirm that wages and salaries significantly impact quality performance. This supports the hypothesis that there is a strong positive relationship between wages and salaries and the quality performance of local governments.

Hypothesis 3: There is a Strong Positive Relationship between Recognition and Creativity Performance in Local Governments in Anambra State, Nigeria

Table 3: Regression Analysis for Recognition and Creativity Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.756	0.179	9.808	0.000
Recognition	0.522	0.065	0.403	0.002

The regression analysis reveals that recognition has a positive impact on creativity performance. The coefficient for recognition ($B = 0.522$) suggests that increased recognition leads to better creativity performance in local government employees. The t-value (9.808) and the significance level of 0.002 (less than 0.05) confirm that recognition significantly influences creativity performance. This supports the hypothesis that recognition positively influences creativity performance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the regression analysis confirm that all three hypotheses are supported. First, promotion was found to have a significant positive influence on innovative performance, meaning that when employees are promoted, they are likely to engage in more innovative activities, contributing to the overall progress of the local government. This aligns with previous studies (Kuvaas, 2021) that highlight the role of career advancement in motivating employees to innovate. Second, the analysis shows a strong positive relationship between wages and salaries and quality performance. This finding emphasizes the importance of fair compensation in improving the quality of work

and performance in local government settings. Studies such as those by Meier and O'Toole (2020) confirm that competitive wages lead to higher employee satisfaction and better performance outcomes. Lastly, the relationship between recognition and creativity performance was also found to be significant. Recognition serves as a motivator, encouraging employees to be more creative and innovative in their roles. This result is in line with findings from authors like Grant and Parker (2020), who argue that employee recognition drives creativity and fosters a culture of innovation within organizations. The results of this study underscore the importance of compensation components—promotion, wages and salaries, and recognition—in driving performance outcomes such as innovation, quality, and creativity. These findings suggest that local governments in Anambra State should consider enhancing their compensation strategies to foster a more productive and performance-oriented workforce.

Summary of Findings

The study examined the influence of promotion, wages and salaries, and recognition on the performance of local governments in Anambra State,

Nigeria, with a focus on innovative performance, quality performance, and creativity performance. The key findings from the data analysis are as follows: The study found a significant positive relationship between promotion and innovative performance. Promotion positively influenced the ability of local government employees to engage in innovative activities, thereby enhancing overall performance. A strong positive relationship was established between wages and salaries and the quality performance of local governments. Higher wages and salaries contributed significantly to improved quality of work and better outcomes in local government activities. Recognition was found to have a positive impact on creativity performance. Employees who received recognition were more likely to engage in creative activities, which contributed to enhanced performance in their roles.

Conclusion

The findings from this study provide strong evidence that promotion, wages and salaries, and recognition are critical factors influencing the performance of local governments in Anambra State. These factors not only motivate employees but also directly affect their innovative capabilities, quality of work, and

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creativity. Local governments that invest in these aspects of employee compensation and recognition are likely to experience better overall performance and outcomes in service delivery.

Recommendations

Enhance Promotion Opportunities: Local governments in Anambra State should establish clear career progression frameworks to motivate employees. Regular promotions and opportunities for advancement can foster a culture of innovation, as employees will be more inclined to contribute creative solutions to the organization.

Improve Wages and Salaries: To enhance the quality performance of local government employees, there is a need to review and increase wages and salaries. Competitive compensation packages can attract and retain skilled workers, ensuring better outcomes in public service delivery.

Increase Employee Recognition Programs: Local governments should develop formal recognition programs that acknowledge employees' efforts and achievements. Recognizing and rewarding creativity and hard work can significantly boost employee morale and encourage continuous improvement in performance.

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